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Effects Of Resilience Counseling Techniques On Test Anxiety And Academic Performance Among Students Of Selected College of Education in North East Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine the effects of resilience counseling technique on test anxiety and academic performance among students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua , Yobe State in North-eastern Nigeria. The study used quasi-experimental design in form of pretest, and posttest. The population of this study was the students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua , Yobe State in North-eastern Nigeria and 238 students were identified with symptoms of Test anxiety. Equally sixty 60 students was used as sample of the study, they were purposely selected to participate in the study. The study used researchers developed instrument for data collection titled Students Test Anxiety Identification Checklist (STAIC). Frequency and Percentage and independent t-test was used in the analysis of data. The findings of this study revealed that there was high prevalence of test anxiety among students of Umar Suleiman College of Education. Also there is no significant gender difference in test anxiety between male and female students of Umar Suleiman College of education Gashua College The study revealed that resilience counselling technique has positive effect on test anxiety. Also the finding of this study shows that resilience counselling technique improves students' academic performance. The study concluded that resilience counselling technique was effective in minimizing test anxiety and improves the performance of NCE I students in Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua. Finally the study recommended that students needs appropriate counseling intervention.

Keywords: Resilience Counseling Test-Anxiety Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the major aspect and instruments used for the well-being of the society in all dimensions; economically, socially and politically as well as technologically. It is for this reason that much emphasis is attached to its acquisition at all times and at different levels. Thus, a person's education

is closely related to his/her life chances, income and well-being. Education is provided at various levels and one of these levels is Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE Programme). This programme is rigorous and demands adequate time and attention on the side of students taking into cognizance the number of courses being offered, nature of lectures and intensity of the training. Students that take part in such programme include newly admitted students and old students among others (Muktar and Gishiwa 2020).

The main objective of every teaching-learning interaction is to bring about harmonious development of the individual and acquisition of desired knowledge, values and skills to enable the learner to function in a particular way. The outcome of successful acquisition of knowledge and skills in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains are measured through series of tests and examinations after a period of instructions and it is referred as academic achievement (Muktar & Gishiwa, 2020). It can also be described as the outcome of education, that is the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved educational goals. Jackson, (2010) lamented that the beginning of NCE programme can be a significant life transition in which people's abilities to adjust may be challenging. Newly admitted students who are commencing NCE programmes somehow they are unfamiliar with the campus life often find the experience to be not only new, but also frightening and difficult to deal with it.

In our Colleges of Education most of the students admitted are from secondary schools in the rural areas where interaction is homogeneous in nature and these categories of students lack tertiary institutions experiences like how to take lectures, writing an assignment and testes as well as examination among others. As such, most of the students find it difficult to adjust and many among them begin to develop anxiety particularly in relation to taking tests and examinations. Test anxiety is one of the most common psychological disorders in school aged children and adolescents worldwide. It is associated with substantial negative effects on students, social, emotional, intellectual and academic success (Thakur, 2016).

In an attempt to address this issue, the Students Affairs Division in the Colleges in North eastern States usually make efforts to ameliorate such condition by, organizing annual orientation lectures for the newly admitted students. These orientation lectures are crucial in assisting the students to cope with some challenges they are facing during their first interactions in the colleges like registration processes, booking accommodations, locating library and became aware of college rules and regulation as well as to know lecture venues, among others.

Equally, the Guidance and Counselling centres in the various Colleges usually follow up with additional support services to such categories of students (fresher's) to sensitize them and counsel them on their feelings and perceptions about academic and other activities in the colleges. From the records of guidance and counselling units of the colleges in the North eastern States, students are still displaying their fears and worries about their stay in the institutions.

The present study was carried out to find out students levels of resilience, prevalence of test anxiety and effect of resilience counselling techniques on test anxiety among them.

Statement of the Problem

Certainly various studies justified that numerous factors and conditions of learning bring about anxiety among students particularly fresh students when they are expecting test or examination in the Colleges (Javed & Khan 2020). Also George, (2018 in Khan and Javed 2020) lamented that test provoke anxiety in some students at different level. Certainly students have examination phobia when taking or writing examination, some students may experience negative thoughts or fear of failure and at most time develop unpleasant physical symptoms which prevent them from performing well.

Test and examinations in the Colleges of Education are likely to cause anxiety among fresh students because it is often being the first time these students experienced such kind of evaluation of their performance and thus makes them to exhibit certain level of anxiety and phobia due to lack of social support, intensive orientation and exposure as well as resilience building. Inadequate ideas on how the test and exams are conducted and problem of adjustment in the Colleges are among the factors that cause test anxiety and other academic stress among students in the Colleges of Education in the North-East.

Equally, newly admitted students are not in exception to phobia particularly when tests or examination time table are released. Students may begin to express concerns, worries and their fear toward tests. These

and other related factors are as a result of new transition from basic education to higher education and as a result of maladjustment to university life among others.

Bako (2025) who observed that, many students were seen to be physically, mentally and emotionally stable while taking normal regular lectures but as soon as continuous assessments tests commenced and examination approaches, or examination time table was pasted, one would notice a drastic change in their normal mood. They continued to experience feelings of tension and fear before, during and after the examination exercise. Test significantly becomes a source of worry to many students and due to this intense fear, some become psychologically devastated and emotionally imbalance to the extent that some felt sick; and others shows displeasure. However, same time some students displayed significant physical symptoms like, sweating, dry mouth, hands shaking, stammering, headache and in severe case feverish condition which prevent them from writing the exams and performing well to the best of their ability.

Objectives of the study

The research intends to achieve the following objectives:

- 1) To find out the prevalence of test anxiety among NCE I students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua Yobe State in North-eastern Nigeria.
- 2) To determine gender difference on test anxiety among NCE I students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua Yobe State in North-eastern Nigeria.
- 3) To determine the effectiveness of Counselling technique on test anxiety and Academic performance of NCE I students of Umar Suleiman Colleges of Education Gashua Yobe State in North-eastern Nigeria

Research Questions

The study attempted to answer the following research question

- 1) What is the prevalence of test anxiety among among NCE I students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua Yobe State in North-eastern Nigeria.

Hypothesis

Null hypotheses was formulated to guide the study as follows

H₀₁ There is no significant any gender difference on test anxiety among among NCE I students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua Yobe State in North-eastern Nigeria.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic dimension of test anxiety among NCE I Students of Umar Suleiman College Education Gashua in Yobe State Nigeria exposed to resilience counseling technique

LITERATURE REVIEW

Resilience Counseling Technique

Resilience counseling techniques refers to the therapeutic approach aimed to help individual recovery from stressful life events. Resilience counseling techniques also mean a counseling strategies designed to assist individual adapt to adversity, manage life stress, and ability to recover from traumatic events. Therefore, resilience counseling technique is a counseling model designed to improve individual abilities to control oneself from stressful experience or condition and build up protective skills and courage to manage the situation.

Using a resilience counseling technique based on a broad range of research evidence across domains and years of practical experience, different techniques can be employing as a strategic methodology to support disadvantaged children and young people in overcoming adversity (Claire & Hart 2020).

Resilience counseling techniques is effective and recommended for the treatment of phobia and for academic success. It helps to overcome different challenges facing students during training, examination and coping positively with stress in life (Muktar, et al 2023). Resilient students report greater well-being including a positive outlook about their learning environment, good quality of life and academic achievement. The effectiveness of resilience Counseling technique in the treatment of phobia and academic success was mentioned in various studied Lekan, Ward & Elliot (2018) mentioned that focusing on inclusion of resilience counseling in nursing curriculum is necessary to ensure that students are well prepared to succeeded academically and transition smoothly into their proportional roles. Also, in line this

hwang and shin (2018) Academic resilience is vital for the emotional wellbeing of students in higher education. They also found that a large proportion of nursing students with high academic resilience levels had higher academic grades.

Wagnild, (2011) described resilience as a response to adversity where an individual's original state is disturbed by the adversity experienced but the individual is able to re-establish equilibrium at a different level than the original state. According to Sullivan in Chen (2018), Resilience is traditionally viewed as a protective mechanism deployed when facing external distress. Chen. (2014), referred to resilience as the ability that enable individual to overcome or adapt to adversity and create positive outcomes across the duration of the interaction with their environment. Resilience is the capacity to recoil from life's stressors.

In addition, resilience is made up of five important pillars that significantly enhance individual levels of resilience. (Hart & Havear, 2013). These are:

- I. Self-awareness
- II. Mindfulness
- III. Self-care
- IV. Positive relationships
- V. Purpose

Test anxiety

Test anxiety is defined as unpleasant state characterize by the feeling of tension or uneasiness that usually occur before a scheduled test. Test anxiety is seen as that nervous feeling students get when about to take test. Test anxiety is a psychological condition in which students experience extreme distress and anxiety in testing situation (Kendra, 2023). Zeidner (2004) stated that early conceptions viewed test anxiety as a uni-dimensional construct; but recent researches indicated that test anxiety is multi-dimensional in nature. The symptoms of test anxiety manifest in different dimensions ranging from physiological, cognitive and emotional. The symptoms that manifest in students through physiological dimension include sweating, headache, stomach upset, handshake, heartbeat and dried mouth; the symptoms that manifest in students through cognitive dimension include forgetfulness, feeling of uncertainty and unsatisfactory score and other irrational thinking; and the symptoms that manifest in students through emotional dimension include fear, loss of comfort, lack of concentration, making careless mistakes, and constant time checking.

Kavakci, Semiz, Kartal, Dikici and Kugu (2018) carried out a study on test anxiety prevalence and related variables in the students who are going to take the university entrance examination. The purpose of this study was to test anxiety among students and its diverse effect on students' academic performance. The objectives of the study were to find out the prevalence of test anxiety among students. The second objective was to identify the predictors of test anxiety and the related variables among students who were going to take the university entrance examination. Descriptive study design was used. The population of the study was 15700 who take the university entrance examination. 436 students were randomly selected which comprised 220 females and 216 males from different schools. The instrument used for data collection was socio demographic form and Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI) Beck Depression Inventory (BDI) State Traits Anxiety Inventory (SATI). The study finding revealed that approximately half of the students 48.3 % were found with moderate level of test/ examination anxiety. The study concluded that the prevalence of examination anxiety was higher. Therefore, the study recommended that test anxiety prevention program should be organized to minimize depression and examination anxiety among students.

Thakur (2016) carried out a comparative study of examination phobia among boys and girls in rural and urban higher secondary school in Raipur (India). The general objective of this study was to find out the significance differences in examination phobia among boys and girls in higher secondary schools. The specific objectives were to measure the prevalence of examination phobia among boys in higher secondary schools in the rural area, determine the causes related to examination phobia among girls in higher secondary schools in the rural area. Find out the causes related to examination phobia among boys in higher secondary school in the urban area. To measure the causes related to examination phobia among

girls students at higher secondary schools in the urban area, and to compare the causes related to examination phobia between boys and girls students of rural and urban areas. The design of the study was descriptive survey. The population of the study was 187 and the sample size was 126 participants. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire. Mean and standard deviation and t-test was used in the analysis. The result revealed that there was no significant difference between boys and girls in the causes of examination phobia in higher secondary school. The finding also showed that location (rural or urban area) was not a significant factor in examination phobia among students in higher secondary school in Raipur India. The study recommended that relaxation techniques, bio feedback (to control stress and muscle tension) family therapy, parents training and meditation as well as healthy atmosphere for students should be provided to help students.

Khan and Javed (2020) conducted a research on the impact of examination fear on secondary schools students' self-esteem in Karachi Pakistan. The objectives of the study were to determine the prevalence and to identify the factors which cause examination fear among secondary school students, to find out prevalence of examination fear on secondary school students self –esteem. The study used survey research design. The study adopted mixed method where questionnaire and interview were used as the instruments of data collection. The researcher used convenient random sampling technique and 138 students were selected to participate in the study. Quantitative data from the questionnaire were analysed through statistical package of social science (SPSS) 22. The study found that greater percentage of students 73% exhibited symptoms of examination phobia. The study also revealed that lack of social support, poor parental and teacher/ students relationship were among the factors that caused examination phobia among students. The study recommended that Guidance and Counselling Services should be provided to help students. Equally, parent's teachers and student's relationship should be improved.

In a study conducted by Hanfesa, Tilahun, Dessie, Shumet, and Salelew, (2020) on test anxiety and associated factors among first-year Health Science students. The objective of the study was to assess the prevalence of test anxiety and associated factors among first-year regular undergraduate health science students of the University of Gondar, northwest Ethiopia. The method adopted in this research was an institutional-based cross-sectional study using survey design. The population of the study was 813 and the sample size used in the study was 349 first year students selected using stratified random sampling technique. The results of this study revealed that, test anxiety was 54.7% among first year students in the University of Gondar. The study concluded that test anxiety was a major problem of first-year undergraduate health science students.

In another study conducted by Lawal, Idemudia, and Adewale, (2017) on academic self-confidence (Resilience) effects on test anxiety among Nigerian university students. The study investigated academic self-confidence effects on test anxiety as indicators of performance impairment and intrusive worry. The population of the study was 206 Nigerian undergraduate students comprising males and females. The students took the Westside Test Anxiety Scale as instrument of data collection administered by the researchers. Data were analyzed to predict performance impairment and intrusive worry from academic self-confidence, taking into account student's years of study and gender. The study results indicated that, first year students reported higher intrusive worry than those in second, third and fourth year of studies in the university.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research adopted a quasi-experimental design inform of Pre-test and Post-test design to examine the effects of resilience counseling techniques on test anxiety and academic performance among students of Umar Suleiman Colleges of education in North-Eastern Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design aims to establish cause-and-effect relationship between the independent and dependent variable. It involves manipulation of one or more independent variable(s) on the dependent variable(s) but without random assignment of subjects to condition. This design was deem fit for this study because the two independents variables, Resilience Counseling technique was manipulated to determine its effectiveness on test anxiety among students of Umar Suleiman College of Education in North-Eastern State, Nigeria.

Diagrammatical representation of the design

The population of this study consists of 434 NCE one students of Umar Suleiman Colleges of Education Gashua Yobe State in North-East Nigeria. NCE one students who were newly admitted participated in this study. Therefore, the target population was selected among those students identified with the symptoms of test anxiety which comprises 238 and sixty 60 student were sampled as treatment group,

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting the subjects among students bin the Colleges. Purposive sampling was employed because it is a strategy in which particular settings, person or events are selected deliberately in order to provide important information that cannot be obtained from other choices (Maxwell cited in Abdullahi 2022).

Data Collection Instrument

The study used researcher’s-developed instruments for identification of students having test anxiety and for data collection for this study, namely, Students Test Anxiety Identification Checklist (STAIC). The instrument has two sections, A and B. Section A sought information on students personal data and section B contained twenty (20) items which sought information used in answering research question and testing of research hypothesis. Face and construct validity of the instrument was done to determine the validity of the research instrument by experts from Guidance and Counseling, Test and Measurement Department, Bayero University Kano for ascertaining the appropriateness of the items in relation to the research objective and hypothesis formulated for the study, relevance, adequacy and the language used in the instruments .

However, the Cronbach alpha Coefficient of reliability was used in assessing the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument was found valid and reliable at 0.89 reliability coefficient.

RESULTS OF THE STUDY

The study investigates the effects of resilience counselling techniques on test anxiety and academic performance among students of Umar Suleiman Colleges of Education Gashua Yobe State-Nigeria. This chapter presents the analysis of data collected from samples of the study. The data were presented in tables. Analyses were done based on descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics via frequency counts and percentages were used to calculate the prevalence rate of Test anxiety. T-test was used to test null hypothesis 1 and the decision for rejection or acceptance was based on 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Summary of participants by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1. Male	24	40.0%
2. Female	36	60.0%
Total	60	100.0%

Table 1 shows distribution of respondents according to gender. It shows that there were 24 male respondents representing 40% and 36 female representing 60% for the study.

Answers to Research Question

In order to answer this research question, the data collected were subjected to frequency counts and simple percentage. This was done in order to identify the prevalence and levels of test anxiety among students (NCEI) of Umar Suleiman Colleges of Education Gashua Yobe State, Nigeria.

Research Question 1: *What is the prevalence rate of test anxiety among students of Umar Suleiman Colleges of Education Gashua Yobe State, in North-east Nigeria?*

Table 2 prevalence of Test Anxiety

Level	Frequency	Percentage
High	238	55%
Low	196	45%
Total	434	100%

Source: Field work (2025)

Table 2 above showed the descriptive statistics on the prevalence of test anxiety among NCE I students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua in Yobe State, Nigeria. It shows that out of the total number of 443 instruments administered to the target respondents a total number of 434 were returned out of which two hundred and thirty eight 238 respondents representing 55% were identified with high symptoms of test anxiety while the remaining 196 respondents representing 45% were not met the criteria for selection. Therefore, the above analysis revealed that, the prevalence of test anxiety among NCE I students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua in Yobe State Northeast, Nigeria was high at 55%.

The findings of this study align with Bako (2025) who reported that there is prevalence of test anxiety and examination phobia among students of higher institutions of Kaduna State. Also the results of this study affirm the findings of Khan and Jave (2018) which says majority of undergraduates students in their first year of studies manifested the symptoms of test anxiety.. Equally the findings of this study align with the view of Ruwam, (2008) in Omege (2018) that test anxiety is a self-damaging factor which negatively affects students and their performances. Student having test anxiety is unable to give his maximum productivity and the end result would be critical. A person who demonstrates typically low rates of test/examination confidence when partaking with others such as classmates on a given test/examination has test anxiety or examination phobia. Equally in the points of Oparanozie, (2016). Test anxiety has serious negative implication on students experiencing it. It could mar or rather jeopardize students' future, thereby creating nuisance such as test avoidance or malpractice. Like many other anxiety disorders, epidemiological investigations have consistently revealed a greater proportion of females than males with specific phobia. She further stated that females manifest test anxiety more than their male counterparts and that as a means of escaping from such situations both gender resorts to test or examination malpractices. Similarly the findings of this study confirm the findings of Muktar, Auwal and Bello (2025) that, there is prevalence of test anxiety among level 100 students in universities in Yobe State. And the the categories of these students needs special counseling intervention to minimize this problem among students

H₀₁: There is no significant any gender difference on test anxiety among among NCE I students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua Yobe State in North-eastern Nigeria.

Table 3: t-test for Independent Sample between Male and Female respondents in the level of test anxiety

Gender	N	Mean	SD	T	DF	P
Male	37	62.49	7.09	-1.981	58	.052
Female	23	66.43	8.13425			

NS at .052 ≥ 0.05

Table 3 presents the results for gender difference in the mean scores of test anxiety among NCE I Students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua in Yobe State North east Nigeria. The finding reveal that no significant difference was found ($t=-.819$, $DF=28$, $p =.419$), indicating that there is no significant difference in the mean scores of test anxiety between male and female NCE I Students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua in Yobe State Nigeria. Therefore the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the level of test anxiety between male and female NCE I Students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua in Yobe State North east Nigeria is retained.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic dimension of test anxiety among NCE I Students of Umar Suleiman College Education Gashua in Yobe State Nigeria exposed to resilience counseling technique.

Table 4: Paired Sample t-test for pre-test and post-test scores on academic dimension of examination phobia

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Df	P-Value
Pretest academic	24	15.92	2.104	17.603	23	.000
Posttest academic		6.96	1.367			

Sig at P 0.00 ≤ 0.05

Table 4 show the results for pretest and posttest mean scores of academic dimension of test anxiety among NCE I Students, the findings revealed that a significant difference between the mean scores was found ($t(23) = 17.603, P = .000$) indicating that there is significant effect of resilience counselling technique on academic dimension ($M = 15.92$ and 6.96), therefore the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic dimension of test anxiety among NCE I Students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua in Yobe State, Nigeria exposed to resilience counseling technique is rejected.

Ahmed, Hussain and Khan (2015) conducted a study on the effect of Resilience counseling technique on test anxiety among students of University Islamabad Pakistan. The study attempted to explore the causes and prevalence of test anxiety among students of University Islamabad Pakistan. The study discovered that the prevalence of test anxiety was high at 67% among the students of University of Islamabad. However, female students have more test anxiety as compared to males' students. The study also revealed that the major causes of test anxiety and exam phobia arise from parental attitudes, expectation of high grades, and admission in good institutions, job market, and work load, lack of preparation, inappropriate test techniques and home-school maladjustment. The study recommended that this problem may be addressed through simulation, yoga, behavior modification, therapeutic approaches, guidance and counseling especially resilience counseling technique. Similarly the findings of this study align with Omega et al, (2018) who lamented that more than 50% of students in first year of studies in Colleges and Universities have higher test anxiety and examination phobia. However,. Equally, the findings of this study correspond with Sunny (2021) carried out a study on resilience counselling on examination phobia, and academic performance among students in tertiary institutions The purpose of this study was To find out the prevalence rate of test anxiety and examination phobia among students. The study finding revealed that approximately more than half of the students 58.3 % were found with high level of test anxiety and exam phobia. Also the study revealed that resilience counseling technique was effective on all the dimension of test anxiety and examination Phobia.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the prevalence of test anxiety was higher. Also there is no significant gender difference in the level of test anxiety between male and female students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State North east Nigeria. Equally, resilience counseling technique was very effective in minimizing the level of Test anxiety among NCE I students of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua Yobe State.

RECOMMENDATION

The study recommended that test anxiety prevention program should be organized to minimize depression among students. Similarly annual orientation lectures for newly admitted students should be organized to sensitize students. The study also recommended that resilience and exposure counseling techniques will be combine as counseling intervention to those students found with symptoms of test anxiety.

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